

02 On Discrete Euclidean Space

Sydney Ernest Grimm*

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The paper is the second post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>.

The first post was about the origin of the constant speed of light, the second post is about the existence of a minimal length scale and the quantum of energy.

3D pixels

The previous blog post shows an image of a blade of grass, inclusive a square metric. The existence of a spatial metric in our universe is not a new idea although the size of this fundamental length and the spatial structure that creates the metric isn't determined. In the first half of the 20th century theorists like W. Heisenberg^[1], H.T. Flint^[2], A. March^[3], F. Möglich^[4], S. Goudsmit^[5] and others proposed the existence of a minimal length scale, a metric that corresponds with the size of particles and the shortest wave length of electromagnetic waves ($\lambda \approx 1 \times 10^{-15}$ m). However, the wave length of an electromagnetic wave envelopes 2 corresponding amplitudes. That is why the metric of the minimal length scale must be about $0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m. See figure 1 below.

The existence of a minimal length scale in the universe means that the volume of our universe must be quantized. That indicates the universe is a volume that is composed of “3D pixels”, small volumes that share the same basic properties and all these volumes together tessellate the universe. Or to say it in a concrete way, Euclidean space itself is discreet.

figure 1

There is direct evidence that shows the existence of discrete space itself and it is determined in the equation of the Planck-Einstein relation (electromagnetic waves):

$$E = h f = \frac{h c}{\lambda} \quad (1)$$

Energy (E) is an amount of change in relation to everything around that is determined by the periodicity (f) of the electromagnetic wave. Because energy is quantized, the Planck constant (h). Planck's constant represents a small amount of energy: $4,135667696 \times 10^{-15}$ eV·s.

The frequency (f) of an electromagnetic wave is a number. Because Planck's constant represents a whole wave length the total amount of energy of an electromagnetic wave is always $E = n h$, whereby the number n is an integer.

If we examine the Planck-Einstein relation (1) we have to conclude that the only variable in the whole equation is the wave length (λ). But this is logical inconceivable. Because the equation shows that the variable wave length must be a constant length or a multiple of a constant length ($\lambda = n l_c$). The only logical conclusion is the existence of a standard metric in space, the minimal length scale.

One can argue that changes within observable reality show smooth transitions so it is hard to imagine that the volume of space itself is really quantized. But smooth transitions are not surprising if the metric has a size of $\approx 0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m and the structure of space itself is in rest in relation to the transferred phenomena. Moreover, if reality is really homogeneous there exist no variance in the universe.

The existence of the minimal length scale is confirmed in the Standard model of elementary particles and forces. Because at a scale smaller than $\approx 0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m there are no observable distinct phenomena any more. The anomaly is termed asymptotic freedom and is thought to be the cause behind the impossibility to detect solitary quarks, the proposed constituents of hadrons. Actually, quantum chromodynamics (QCD) was constructed to by-pass the experimental evidence that reductionism had come to an end.^[6]

References:

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The quantum of energy

If Euclidean space is discrete I can draw a schematic representation of a part of the volume of the universe. The image in figure 2 shows a volume with the hypothetical structure, determined by the minimal length scale (l_c). It isn't said that the size and shape of every “3D pixel” corresponds with reality. The only similarity is the composition of the volume with the help of units with identical basic properties. Units that tessellate the enveloping volume.

figure 2

A dynamical volume that is tessellated by units with the same basic properties is not really common in daily live. Actually, this is quite a new concept of reality nowadays because in our culture we are used to the phenomenological point of view. That means observable phenomena can

change their position independently from the “emptiness” around. Nevertheless, figure 2 shows that every change in our universe depends on the synchronous change of everything else around. Therefore it is necessary to focus on the mathematical consequences of the properties of the units of discreet Euclidean space.

figure 3

What we have termed “energy” in physics is another term for “change”. And the main law in physics is the law of conservation of energy. In other words, all the change in our universe is conserved.

Figure 2 shows a schematic representation of the underlying structure of our universe. Unfortunately, this is not how we observe reality. Because what we call reality are the *mutual relations* between the observable phenomena in the universe. But it is obvious that the “law of conservation of change” applies also to the underlying structure of discreet space. Because it is the underlying structure that creates observable reality.

If I want to apply change to the units in figure 2 I have to change the shape of the units. All the units tessellate space thus changing the shape of one unit is only possible if the shapes of all the units in the universe are changing synchronously. That is only possible if the volume of every unit is identical and invariant.

Figure 3 shows one schematic unit and each side of the cube has an arrow that represents the direction of the deformation of the distinct side. The volume of the cube is invariant thus the total amount of the transfer of volume (ΔV) inside the cube is conserved. Therefore:

$$\Delta V_A + \Delta V_B = \Delta V_C + \Delta V_D + \Delta V_E + \Delta V_F$$

or generalized:

$$\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$$

figure 4

The change of the shape of an invariant volume is termed a [homeomorphism](#) in the mathematical field of topology. Moreover, the change has to be smooth and synchronous because to keep the volume invariant the change of the shape will always envelope 2 or more synchronous deformations of the volume. Figure 4 shows the principle: the cross section of the deformation of 2 identical invariant volumes with a joint surface area.

However, if the deformation of the shape of a unit of discrete space is a smooth and synchronous topological deformation, how is it possible that experiments have showed that energy is quantized?

Figure 5 shows the top view of a bar magnet with a sheet of paper and iron powder. In this way we can observe the influence of the magnetic field around the iron bar. The local magnetic field shows a sort of a loop between the North pole and the South pole of the magnet. Actually, it represents just $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$

The magnet is not at rest, the magnet moves in relation to the underlying structure of discrete space. The consequence is that during the continuous and synchronous change of their shapes the units of discrete space constantly have to switch their input and output faces. All the deformations of the units of discrete space in the universe are synchronized thus there exist a quantum of topological

figure 5

deformation. That means the transfer of a fixed amount of volume during a fixed amount of time. Observable reality is limited to the mutual relations between the phenomena and that is why the mutual changes are quantized: Planck's constant (h).

In other words, the topological deformation – energy – as a basic property of the units of discrete space isn't quantized, the mutual relations between the observable phenomena are quantized. The continuous and synchronous deformation of all the units of discrete space is totally smooth.

In the past the law of conservation of energy was used to explain chemical reactions. The energy before the reaction is always equal to the energy after the reaction. But if all the change in our universe is continuous, synchronized and totally smooth the Standard cosmological model ([\$\Lambda\$ CDM](#)) is seriously flawed.

It is impossible that all the topological deformation in the universe can be concentrated in one point in space and it is also impossible to expand "outer space" because the conservation of energy is the invariance of the dynamical property of all the units of discrete Euclidean space. The red shift of the light of distant galaxies has another causation.